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Author Correction: Comparability of automated drusen volume measurements in age-related macular degeneration: a MACUSTAR study report

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The original version of this Article contained an error in the Methods section, under the subheading ‘Statistical analyses’, where the following sentence has been deleted:

“Furthermore, we calculated the agreement in iAMD based on exceeding a drusen volume cut-off indicating higher AMD progression risk (previously shown at $>0.03 \text{ mm}^3$ for Cirrus, set on Spectralis by adding the mean difference between the two devices to 0.03).”

The original Article has been corrected.

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